

Supplemental Materials for:
Rapid surface-deployment of a DAS system for
earthquake hazard assessment

Joseph Mjehovich^{1,2}, Ge Jin³, Eileen R. Martin^{3,4,5}, and Jeffrey Shragge⁶

¹Geophysicist, IFDATA LLC, 6730 Highclere Manor Ln., Houston, TX, 77055 (corresponding author) Email: jmjehovich@ifdataservices.com

²Former M.S. Student, Dept. of Geophysics, Colorado School of Mines, 1500 Illinois St., Golden, CO, 80401

³Assistant Professor, Dept. of Geophysics, Colorado School of Mines, 1500 Illinois St., Golden, CO, 80401

⁴Assistant Professor, Dept. of Applied Mathematics and Statistics, Colorado School of Mines, 1500 Illinois St., Golden, CO, 80401

⁵Assistant Professor, Dept. of Mathematics, Virginia Tech, Blacksburg, VA, 24061

⁶Associate Professor, Dept. of Geophysics, Colorado School of Mines, 1500 Illinois St., Golden, CO, 80401

Table S1: VS30 Numerical Results

Line Segment	Distance N-S (m)	VS30 estimate (m/s)	VR36 peak (m/s)	VR36 picked (m/s)
Concrete North	0	390.01	362.46	362.46
Grass Pressed	7.35	387.89	278.78	360.56
Grass	9.8	387.96	360.56	360.56
Subsurface 1	12.95	379.78	352.95	352.95
Subsurface 2	19.6	344.99	320.62	320.62
Subsurface 3	26.95	336.80	313.01	313.01
Subsurface 4	34.3	340.90	316.82	316.82
Snow Pressed	36.25	336.80	313.82	313.82
Snow	39.2	336.80	313.01	313.01
Concrete South	41.65	344.98	704.80	320.61